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Long-Term-Experiments – methods, standardization, and modelling

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Abstract Long-term field experiments (LTEs) play an important role in studying the effects of different management strategies on the soil ecosystem. However, LTEs are very diverse regarding location, duration, experimental design or research question. Therefore, in October 2020, experts on LTEs from five different European countries met in a virtual workshop to discuss how to ensure high quality in LTE research. Recommendations for the implementation and use of LTEs were drawn from the presentations and discussions based on the following topics: (1) design and statistical evaluation, (2) soil and plant parameters, (3) requirements for data archiving and modelling as well as (4) data management and repository. Furthermore, it was concluded, that international networks enable joint analyses of LTEs to gain a better understanding of long-term changes in crop production at different climate conditions. This knowledge can help to develop sustainable agricultural management strategies. Consequently, a close collaboration among different groups like BonaRes, GLTEN and IOSDV can strengthen the validity of LTE research.

Keywords BonaRes, soil research, long-term experiments, experimental design, soil parameters, plant parameters, modelling, data management

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1 Introduction

Soil is a finite agricultural resource which can be greatly influenced by farm management practices. Therefore, it is important to improve our understanding of the impact of different agri-ecosystems on soil functions and develop strategies for the sustainable use of soil. Long-term experiments (LTEs) play an important role in studying the effects of different management strategies on the soil ecosystem. To better utilise the potential of these experiments, they must be carried out in accordance with scientific standards of agricultural field trials (Ireland 2010, Petersen 1994, Thomas 2006) and the data generated should be archived in accordance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles, to ensure it is kept securely and can be made available for future use (Wilkinson et al., 2016, Johnston & Poulton 2018).

On October 1-2, 2020, a virtual LTE-workshop was held on "LTE research - methods, standardization and modelling" as part of the ongoing [BonaRes](#) research project. The workshop was organized and conducted by the Justus Liebig University Gießen in cooperation with the UFZ-Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research Halle (Saale). A total of forty-seven participants from Germany, Great Britain, Denmark, Poland, and Hungary attended the workshop. The aim was to exchange experiences about the application of modern standards in LTEs and to derive recommendations for the use of LTEs for agri-ecosystem research and modelling. The workshop discussed the requirements for data acquisition and statistical evaluation of LTEs. Methods and selected results for biological, chemical, and physical soil parameters were presented (see [Abstract Book](#) for further information).

Conclusions based on the presentations given and subsequent discussions are outlined below.

2 Experimental design of LTEs and statistical evaluation

When setting up a new field experiment, it is of central importance to consider how the data collected will be used for future statistical analyses. Today, it is state of the art to use a replicated design and to allocate treatments to plots randomly. The minimum number of replications per treatment is two to allow a valid estimate of the error variance. The appropriate number of replications depends on the desired precision (Steel et al. 1997). Typical replication numbers used with recently established LTE range from three to four. However, many LTEs, which were established decades or even more than a hundred years ago, do not employ a randomized design. Moreover, some of these LTEs have no true replication or they show a systematic arrangement of the treatments and therefore they are not randomised (Macholdt et al., 2020; Piepho and Vo-Thanh, 2020).

This raises questions about how to deal with data from non-replicated and/or non-randomised LTEs. Despite problems with the experimental design of some early LTEs they are a valuable source of data which allows us to look at changes over time, to gain a better understanding of the effects of management changes and the impact of climate change (Macdonald et al., 2020), and to assess stability and resilience (Reckling et al. 2021). In addition, time series methods are useful to account for serial correlation in these data (Onofri et al., 2016; Payne, 2015).

Even if statistical evaluation of a single non-replicated field trial is not possible, similar non-replicated experiments from different sites can be analysed together. In this case, one option for analysis is to consider each site as a replicate, as is done by companies conducting multi-site on-farm experiments (Piepho et al., 2011). Yet, this approach has not been widely applied to LTEs. The [BonaRes Repository](#) can be used as a data source, stored within a standardized data base scheme, for joint analysis of non-replicated LTEs from different sites in Germany (Grosse et al., 2020a). The challenge posed by such data from multiple sites is reminiscent of what is quite common in meta-analysis (Gurevitch et al. 2018).

Some LTEs in Germany were established using the “response surface method” as proposed by Mitscherlich and von Boguslawski in the 1940s (von Boguslawski, 1942). In this two-dimensional design, one factor is allocated in rows and another factor in columns without randomisation. This analysis does necessitate a systematic design because it is based on the idea to super-impose a sliding window that can be used for block adjustments. The systematic design ensures that the sliding block always comprises the complete set of treatments. In addition to the “classical” evaluation, Piepho and Vo-Thanh (2020) recently found a way to analyse data gained by the response surface method with modern geo-statistical models. This is a promising tool for the evaluation of many LTEs.

3 Criteria for changes in crop species and cultivars

Changes in crop species

The change of plant species during the course of an LTE is often necessary and must be considered in the overall experimental design. Consequently, the replacement of one plant species by another must be well justified from a technical point of view. A short-term change in the crop grown may be a result of damage to the original crop, e. g. due to frost or damage by pests or diseases. Such events may result in the total loss of results for one year. Sometimes, however, it is possible to re-sow the crop if the initial crop failed, e. g. in the event of extremely poor emergence of the seedlings or frost damage. In such cases winter barley or winter wheat may be replaced by spring barley or spring wheat. The failure of maize and sugar beet because of the patchy emergence of the seedlings could also be compensated for by sowing the same species again.

Another factor that can lead to changes in the plant species in an LTE is climate change, particularly heat and drought stress or heavy rainfall. It is recognized that in some LTEs in countries of Southeast Europe problems occur with sugar beets and that these have been exchanged for corn or sunflower within a crop rotation. An example for such a change is the LTE IOSDV (International Organic Nitrogen Fertilisation Experiment) in Iasi (Romania, continental climate), in which the rotational crop sequence sugar beet, winter wheat, winter barley has been replaced by sunflowers, winter wheat, and winter barley (Slabu, 2019). Another example of a climate and agronomically related change in experimental design is the Sewage Sludge Compost (SSC) LTE in Hungary. One of the goals of this LTE is to study the effects of sewage, sludge and compost on the yield and quality of different crop species to contribute to how these organic materials can be incorporated into cropping systems.

Therefore, after 15 years, the green pea was replaced by a mixture of triticale and hairy vetch, rye by triticale and a maize hybrid by another hybrid.

These changes represent an intervention in the experimental design and must be considered when evaluating long-term data series. On the other hand, this measure can be tolerated if it helps to maintain the overall experiment.

Changes in cultivars

Crop cultivars are the result of many years of breeding work and a subsequent three-year value test in multi-environment trials. The currently approved varieties reflect the current progress in plant breeding and represent the highest potential yield at the time that can be used in practical cultivation. Based on genetic information and the variety tests carried out, precise information about the botanical and agronomic properties of the cultivars is available.

In most countries, crop performance tests are conducted annually to provide farmers and further interested organisations and experts with agronomic information. The test results which are mostly conducted by government organizations are usually freely available. In Germany, the official variety tests are carried out by the Federal Plant Variety Office, Hannover, which annually publishes a Descriptive Variety List (<https://www.bundessortenamt.de>). In the UK, recommended lists for cereals and oilseed varieties are provided each year by the Agricultural and Horticulture Development Board, AHDB (<https://ahdb.org.uk/rl>).

Whenever a cultivar is changed, several aspects should be considered carefully. First, the same type of cultivar (hybrid, line, population) should be used, i.e., a wheat line should be replaced by another line but not by a hybrid wheat. Second, it is sensible to replace a cultivar by another one showing similar yield potential and ripening date. Further criteria, depending on the crop species, to be considered, include quality parameters (e. g. baking quality of wheat, barley malting quality, nutritional quality of fodder etc.), nutrient utilization efficiency, disease resistance and the reaction to biotic and abiotic stress (e.g., lodging).

Using the reference cultivar of the official regional variety tests, which is representative for the region, is often useful. To minimize the variety-related variation in yields, it is advisable to select a variety that has been established commercially for 2-3 year, but the final selection will depend on the objectives of the study.

4 Measurement of soil parameters

To characterize the soil conditions under which an LTE is carried out, basic data about the existing soil type according to FAO and IUSS (2015) and about the most important soil properties should be recorded. Thus, it is recommended that before establishing a new LTE, the soil should be evaluated with a steel augur to identify soil heterogeneities within the area of the planned experiment. In addition, it is important to record a soil profile in the immediate vicinity of the LTE. This assessment of the soil should be representative for the site and preferably be performed at the beginning of the LTE. The soil profile should provide valuable information about the formation and characteristics of the soil at the experimental site which includes soil horizons defined by obvious physical features (soil aggregates, soil density), chiefly colour, rooting depth, and soil texture. In addition, further information about the site

(altitude, relief, inclination) and the soil (hydromorphic properties, erosion, carbonates, pH) should also be provided.

The implementation of additional soil analyses which should be carried out while the LTE is in progress, depends on the objective and the design of the experiment. In many cases, comprehensive soil analyses are limited by the available laboratory capacities or the availability of financial support. In the case of low analytical capacities, the number of soil samples could be limited to selected variants or to mixed samples from the variants. However, it is important to make sure that samples allow the assessment of plot-to-plot error. Thus, if pooling is used, there should still be at least two pools per treatment. More complex composite sampling is possible but this needs to be carefully planned (Smith et al., 2011). If there is just one pooled sample per treatment, a valid statistical analysis is not possible, and the data structure is essentially the same as for a non-replicated experiment. In case of a crop rotation, the number of samples could be decreased by yearly sampling the soil of one test plant. In this way, every plot could be sampled in every 3rd or 4th year.

The following are considered to be essential soil parameters: C_t , SOC and N_t , which should be examined regularly in the upper soil horizon (or, depending on the objective, also in lower soil layers), as well as soil texture, bulk density and water holding capacity. Soil mineral N (NO_3^- , NH_4^+) should be sampled annually in spring before fertilizer is applied. Soil pH, available K and P, exchangeable cations, and biological soil characteristics (e. g. earthworm density / biomass, mesofauna abundance, microbial respiration / activity) are also important parameters to measure when evaluating the effects of management on crop production and soil fertility.

Depending on the objectives, different methods can be used to take soil samples. A (stainless) steel augur is usually used for loose samples, which causes a small disturbance of the soil although several punctures per plot into the soil are usually required. In contrast, the use of stainless cylinders represents a considerable interference with the soil, which is why only larger plots or marginal areas are considered for this. The use of a core probe is recommended, with which undisturbed soil samples can be taken from deeper soil layers. For all methods it is important to document the exact GPS position of the sample collection within the plots or experiment.

The plough layer is often the most important layer to sample because the crop receives much of its nutrition from the topsoil and it is mixed regularly. Depending on the research question, however, the subsoil may also be of interest for certain investigations. For example, in experiments with legumes and deep-rooted plants, carbon determinations along the soil profile up to 100 cm are recommended. Favourable dates for taking soil samples in Europe are especially in early spring (at the beginning of vegetation) and after the harvest period in late summer or autumn.

Most of the above-mentioned soil investigations are conducted based on standard methods (in Germany: the VDLUFA method manual) (VDLUFA 1991, 1995, 2011) and have been established for a long time. This also applies to C/N investigations of the soil, which have, however, been further improved in recent years. Besides the dry combustion of soil samples with an elemental analyser, which is considered the standard method for the determination of

Ct, SOC and Nt, several further methods have been developed. Thus, near-infrared (NIR) and mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopic methods are available to determine the amount of carbon stock in the soil (Bellon-Maurel & McBratney 2011). Further on, the method of laser induced break down spectroscopy (LIBS) is currently investigated to quantify soil organic carbon (Nguyen et al., 2015; Nicolodelli et al., 2014).

5 Investigation of soil microbiota

Microorganisms play a significant role in the regulation of biochemical processes in the soil. They are responsible for the degradation of organic matter in the soil and thus release plant available nutrients (NH_4^+ , PO_4^{2-}), they control the processes of mineralization of organically bound nutrients and the immobilization of mineral compounds. They also control the release of carbon from the soil through respiration processes. There are many interactions between microorganisms and plants that have an impact on soil health and plant growth.

LTEs are well suited to investigate the influence of soil use and cultivation management on the microbial processes in the soil. These experiments are therefore increasingly the subject of soil microbiome studies (Bongiorno et al., 2020; Cardinale et al., 2020; Nelkner et al., 2019).

In order to better understand the microbial processes in the soil, modern molecular biological methods are increasingly being used (Clark et al., 2020; Nelkner et al., 2019). Typically, DNA or RNA are extracted from soil samples and PCR-dependent meta-barcode sequencing approaches are in use to deduct the microbial taxa profile (based on partial sequences of the 16S RNA or 18S RNA genes, ITS regions), diversity indices and functional predictions of the microbiome. However, these methods are quite complex, time intensive for the bioinformatic data analysis and require special knowledge of methods, which is why they are not yet suitable as a routine method for soil investigation.

A prerequisite for this investigation is representative soil samples (at least four samples along a diagonal transect of the plot), which are filled into sterile and DNA-free tubes and transported in a cool box. Afterwards, the samples are sieved in the laboratory with a sterile 2 mm sieve and the sieved soil aliquots are frozen at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until DNA extraction. Also, for other microbiological measurements (e. g. soil microbial biomass carbon / SMB-C), the samples must be transported cool in the field and then frozen at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and gradually thawed one day before the measurement. For SMB-C measurements, about 20 g are required (12.5 g for the measurements, 5 g for DM determinations).

To obtain information about the microbial activity in the soil, simple methods should be used. For routine examination of the soil in LTEs, e. g. soil respiration measurements (basal respiration of soil samples, C efflux of soil surface under field conditions) can be carried out. Various measuring devices are available for this purpose, which are equipped with an infrared gas analyser, and which can be used either in the laboratory (soil samples) or under natural field conditions. Also, the potential microbial soil respiration can be routinely measured photometrically in microwell plates with soil to which substrates have been added. Calibration can be done with and without gas analyser and the substrate selection can be adjusted to the research question, e. g. degradation potential of various sugars or organic N-compounds (Campbell et al. 2003).

In addition, so called soil enzymes which are excreted by bacteria, archaea, fungi, and plant roots can be measured to determine the microbial activity in soil. For activities of phosphatase (alkaline and acidic), urease, dehydrogenase and arylsulfatase, various glucosidases protocols have been developed and minimalised (Giacometti et al. 2014). For N₂-fixation activity, nitrification and denitrification activities assays can be used which however require measurements per gas chromatograph over some time and thus are not suitable for routine measurements. A comparatively simple quantitative method is also available for determining the soil microbial biomass C (fumigation method) (Turner et al. 2001).

6 Determination of plant parameters

Aboveground plant biomass is an important indicator of soil properties. Cultivated plants react immediately to any changes in soil properties that are triggered by direct or indirect factors (e. g. mineral fertilization, supply of organic matter, change in pH value, soil tillage). In LTEs the plant biomass should therefore be measured every year on all plots (with at least 10 m² of harvested area), including total aboveground biomass, main and by-products (e.g., grain and straw), water content of the biomass and harvest index. Conventional harvesting methods (e.g., plot combine harvesters) are used to determine the plant biomass. The determination of the plant biomass with the help of drones equipped with multispectral cameras or with other smart farming methods (GPS-supported combine harvesters) cannot yet replace the direct determination of the biomass per plot.

Plants respond to agronomic management practices and soil properties during their development. Response variables include plant height, leaf area and chlorophyll content, number of side shoots, root mass or plant growth stage. For this reason, depending on the design and objective of the experiment, further parameters should be measured during the development of the plants. Some important plant parameters include Leaf area index (LAI), vegetation indices (NDVI, NDRE), chlorophyll index (SPAD), main development stages of the plant (especially anthesis) given as decimal code, yield structure (number of plants, number of shoots, number of grains per plant, thousand grain mass).

7 Economic parameters

LTEs are potentially well suited to perform economic evaluations of the respective production systems. Especially large-scale experiments, like the Rothamsted Large Scale Rotation Experiments, can be translated to an economic analysis relevant to commercial agricultural practice (Macdonald et al., 2020). All management practices, utilised machines and working hours should be recorded carefully. In addition, annual economic indicators including commodity costs, tractor engine hours and labour and produce market value should be considered. This information can serve as basis for further calculations on productivity and profitability.

In addition, LTEs can also be used to provide energy balances of inputs (energy output/input ratio) used in agricultural production systems which can be considered as integrative indicators of environmental effects of respective systems (Hülsbergen et al., 2001). Both individual cultivation measures (e. g. mineral N fertilisation) and entire production systems can be examined regarding their energy balance.

Furthermore, LTEs are also of particular interest for economic assessment of the impact of climate change on agriculture. In this context, risk analyses (Macholdt et al., 2020) and economic efficiency assessments of farming systems (e. g. no-tillage systems, fertilisation systems) can also play an important role (Al-Kaisi et al., 2016; Xia et al., 2014).

9 Requirements for archiving of samples

The archiving of soil and plant samples is of central importance for the long-term evaluation of LTEs. This measure requires appropriate personnel and space or storage capacities, which must be made available. In addition, an exact, standardised, and comprehensible description of samples is required. One of the benefits of sample archiving is that newly developed analysis methods can be used, and interdisciplinary studies can be carried out even after many years. It is of particular importance that, soil and plant samples are available from the beginning of the experiment to be able to describe the initial conditions of the experiment. In order not to overwhelm the storage capacity, it would be sufficient if the samples were only kept from the variants (without repetition) and at intervals of several years. It is important that samples are prepared correctly before archiving to prevent deterioration during storage. Soil samples can be air-dried at room temperature for 5-7 days after collection and milled (<2mm) before storage in cardboard boxes or glass jars. Plant materials (e. g. grain, straw, and herbage) are usually oven-dried (80°C) for 18-48 hrs prior to storage in tins or jars. Some biological procedures may require samples to be stored at extremely low temperatures (-80°C) in specialist facilities.

All archived samples must be labelled with a UUID (universally unique identifier) accession number, and a record submitted to a sample management system. Appropriate sample metadata must be associated with the accession number, including sample date, sample depth, geolocation, experiment plot UUID, sampling method and sample preparation method. The UUID must be referenced in any datasets generated using a sample.

Physical samples are a finite resource, therefore access to samples for laboratory use must be controlled and a condition of access must be a commitment to make any data generated from the sample available for re-use.

10 Requirements for LTEs from a modelling perspective

Depending on the experimental design, the research question and the duration of the experiment, LTEs can be used for different modelling approaches. They can be a basis for modelling crop yields (e.g., yield trends, yield stability), soil processes (e.g., SOC, C sequestration), climate effects (on soil properties and crop yields) or for specialist statistical applications. The focus of this article is on the use of LTEs for modelling soil functions (Vogel et al., 2018).

Modelling of both soil dynamics and crop production requires some key information. For soil, it is important to know the number of horizons, maximum rooting depth, groundwater level, drainage characteristics, initial organic matter, and organic matter input (aboveground and root, both in kg C/ha/year). Each horizon should be characterized specifically according to its texture, content of clay, silt, fine sand, coarse sand, SOC, C:N ratio, bulk density, hydraulic properties etc. Soil pH and deeper boundary conditions (up to 100 cm depth) are also important parameters for modelling of soil dynamics.

Agronomic management should be documented precisely, like soil tillage (depth, kind of machine, date, etc.), sowing density, sowing depth, sowing date, basic and crop specific fertilization (type and concentration of fertilizers, amount of supply, C:N ratio of organic fertilizers, application time), amount, date, and kind of applied pesticides (including active ingredients) and lime and date of harvest. Ideally, dates of development stages and yield components should also be recorded. Additional information required on crop management requires the cultivar used, details of the crop rotation and cover crops (if any) and plant residue management (e. g. removal or incorporation of straw). Additional information includes plot size, size of buffer stripes, biomass production and yield structure.

Plant development is strongly influenced by climatic conditions. Therefore, it is also important to provide data about the location of the experimental site and about specific weather conditions throughout the vegetation period. Information about the experimental site include longitude, latitude, and elevation. Basic weather data should be provided in at least daily resolution: maximum, minimum, and average air temperature, precipitation, wind direction and speed, radiation, or sunshine duration. Furthermore, wet, and dry NH_4^+ and NO_3^- deposition, respectively, can be used in crop modelling. Annual mean meteorological data is also useful to compare sites, e. g. total annual rainfall, mean annual temperature etc., over a specified time, commonly 30 years.

11 Data management and repository

Because of the wide variety of existing LTEs (spatial, temporal, research question, and treatments) and the large number of parameters measured (e.g. yield, soil organic matter, plant nutrient content, climate variables etc.), LTEs produce very complex data sets (Perryman et al., 2018). In many cases data are not well described and are not accessible for third party use, existing in different structures and only in analogue formats (Grosse et al., 2020b). Preparing legacy LTE data for integration into a data repository often requires a lot of data curation effort. Thus, there is an urgent need to improve data collection and curation processes going forward, but also to recognise resourcing data stewardship is an essential requirement for funding LTEs. It is a considerable challenge to compile existing LTE data in a standardized form and make it easily accessible for reuse.

According to the state of the art in international research data management, LTE data should be findable (**F**) for the research community, easily accessible (**A**) by download functions, interoperable (**I**) with other data and repositories, and reusable (**R**) e. g. for modellers. These four requirements are known and described as FAIR data principles in data science (Wilkinson et al., 2016). To meet the FAIR data principles, it is necessary to apply free and widely used standards for all stages of LTE data life, from its acquisition in the field, via its description by metadata, transfer to filing systems or a data repository, until its provision for reuse. Standards facilitate cross-disciplinary data exchange, increase data comparability and visibility, enhance resource efficiencies of data storage, and enable interoperability with data of other national and international infrastructures (Grosse et al., 2020b). To facilitate the exchange and comparability of LTE data, the BonaRes Data Centre developed a uniform, bilingual and relational data base schema to structure data from various LTEs uniformly, including plot and treatment information, data on cultivated crops, varieties and yields, the different activities such

as tillage operations, fertilisation, and plant protection, and finally, meteorological and laboratory data. Before LTE data are published in the BonaRes Repository they must be described by standardized metadata to enhance its findability and reusability (Specka et al., 2019). The BonaRes Repository provides user-friendly data description- and upload tools as well as download functionalities for both data owner and data users (<https://tools.bonares.de/submission/>).

12 Networking

The collective analysis of research data from different LTEs at various locations leads to more generalizable results. Furthermore LTEs are expensive; a comprehensive and coordinated evaluation is also required to justify their expense (Berti et al., 2016; Körschens, 2006).

Networks are valuable for joint analyses. There are international networks such as the working group “Internationale Organische Stickstoffdauerdüngungsversuche” (IOSDV) (Körschens, 2000), the Global Long-Term Experiment Network (GLTEN), which was launched in 2018 (GLTEN, 2020) and networks of organic LTEs like RetiBio in Italy and the RotAB network in France (Ciaccia et al., 2020).

The BonaRes project offers different options for networking among LTEs. The BonaRes Repository can be used jointly and by international data holders. General information about the LTEs is published in an online overview map (<https://lte.bonares.de/experiments/>). The aims of the overview map are to make LTEs more visible, to enhance networking among LTEs and to simplify joint analyses of LTEs. It is available in German and English (Grosse et al., 2020a).

Summary

Long-term field experiments (LTEs) play a significant role in studying the effects of different management strategies on the soil ecosystem. However, LTEs are remarkably diverse regarding location, duration, experimental design, or research question. Therefore, in October 2020, experts on LTEs from five different European countries met in a virtual workshop to discuss how to ensure high quality in LTE research. Recommendations for the implementation and use of LTEs were drawn from the presentations and discussions based on the following topics: (1) design and statistical evaluation, (2) soil and plant parameters, (3) requirements for data archiving and modelling as well as (4) data management and repository. Furthermore, it was concluded, that international networks enable joint analyses of LTEs to gain a better understanding of long-term changes in crop production at different climate conditions. This knowledge can help to develop sustainable agricultural management strategies. Consequently, a close collaboration among different groups like BonaRes, GLTEN and IOSDV can strengthen the validity of LTE research.

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